

Activation Analysis for the Primary Coolant of a Lead Fast Reactor

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ABSTRACT

This work investigates the neutron-induced activation of the primary lead coolant in a low-power, pool-type lead-cooled fast reactor (LFR) representative of a sub-100-MWth technology demonstrator. Even in high-purity heavy-liquid-metal coolants, trace metallic impurities can generate significant long-lived radionuclides under prolonged irradiation, influencing operational radiation fields, maintenance constraints, and end-of-life waste management. To quantify these effects, a SERPENT 2 reactor model was developed to simulate neutron transport, lead depletion, and impurity activation. Two core configurations were assessed: a reference layout surrounded only by reflector assemblies (CORE 1), and a modified layout incorporating additional in-core and ex-core absorber layers (CORE 2) designed to suppress neutron leakage into the reactor pool. Because these shielding additions greatly reduce ex-core fluxes, global variance-reduction techniques based on weighted windows were applied to ensure statistically converged flux estimates in low-intensity regions.

The coolant activation was computed using a multi-zone depletion model with volume-averaged reaction rates. After 40 years of operation, CORE 2 exhibits a reduction in total coolant activity by a factor of four to six compared to CORE 1, depending on the cooling time and dominant isotopes. While most activation products fall below their regulatory exemption limits, ^{108m}Ag consistently emerges as the limiting nuclide. Since silver activation is highly sensitive to its initial concentration, accurate impurity characterization of commercial lead batches is essential for predicting storage and clearance requirements.

Keywords: lead activation, fast reactor, primary coolant, GEN-IV reactor, liquid metal reactor

1. INTRODUCTION

Lead-cooled fast reactors (LFRs) are among the concepts selected within the Generation IV initiative for their favourable safety characteristics, high-temperature capability, and compatibility with closed fuel cycles. Several experimental and demonstration-scale projects are underway in Europe, most notably MYRRHA [1, 2] and ALFRED [3], which aim to advance heavy-liquid-metal technology and provide the operational experience required for future commercial LFRs. In these systems, the primary coolant — high-purity liquid lead or lead–bismuth eutectic — plays a central role not only in heat removal but also in defining key radiological and maintenance constraints.

When exposed to high neutron fluxes over extended periods of irradiation, even small concentrations of metallic impurities in the coolant can generate significant activation products. This has direct implications for: (i) *radiological releases* during normal operation or accidental coolant leakage, (ii) *local gamma fields* impacting in-vessel instrumentation and other sensitive components, (iii) *delayed gamma dose* in ex-core regions during shutdown and maintenance, and (iv) *decommissioning and waste management*, where the activity content of the coolant determines handling requirements, cooling times, and the classification and disposal route of the resulting waste. In particular, a reliable quantification of the radionuclide inventory is essential for evaluating exemption limits, conditioning strategies, and long-term disposal options, as also investigated in recent system studies [4].

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To address these issues, a detailed neutronic model of a lead-cooled fast reactor representative of a low-power technology demonstrator operating below 100 MW_{th} is developed. All neutron transport and lead depletion simulations were performed with the SERPENT 2 Monte Carlo code [5]. Variance-reduction techniques were required to obtain statistically converged flux estimates in low-intensity parts of the system while keeping the computational cost manageable.

Reliable activation predictions further depend on accurate knowledge of elemental impurity concentrations in the coolant, since the activation behaviour is often dominated by trace amounts of species such as cobalt, nickel and silver [6].

The present study reports the resulting activity levels of the lead coolant, identifying the dominant radionuclides. It also compares predicted inventories against exemption limits defined in relevant national regulations [7]. Furthermore, the sensitivity of coolant activation to design choices such as additional in-core and ex-core neutron shielding intended is investigated.

2. CORE LAYOUT

The core layout developed to study the lead primary coolant activation is representative of a low-power, pool-type reactor serving as a heavy-liquid-metal technology demonstrator. It consists of a hexagonal lattice of MOX-fueled assemblies with a uniform plutonium content of 30 wt.% Pu/IHM. The fuel assembly design closely follows that of the MYRRHA fast reactor, as reported in M. Sarotto et al.[2]. The configuration comprises nearly 100 fuel assemblies, sufficient to maintain criticality at a nominal 75 MW thermal power for an approximately 8-month operating cycle, including the effects of fuel burnup in the peripheral assemblies beyond 60 MWd/kg.

In the reference configuration —hereafter CORE 1 — the fuel lattice is surrounded by two crowns of neutron-reflector assemblies that provide both reflection and a degree of spectral moderation. Flux maps obtained for this layout show high neutron flux levels, exceeding $10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, in several ex-core regions such as the reactor pool, where a large volume of liquid lead is present.

To mitigate this neutron leakage, a modified layout — CORE 2 — was developed. In this configuration, two additional rings of high-density neutron absorbers with a macroscopic absorption cross-section of 0.03 cm^{-1} are introduced around the reflector, forming an in-core radial shield, and an annular mid-range absorber is placed ex-core. These shielding enhancements generated a substantial flux reduction in ex-core regions and in the reactor pool, up to three orders of magnitude lower than for CORE 1.

The layouts of the two cores are reported in Figure 1. The following colour scheme is used: blue for the lead-coolant, dark red for the fuel assemblies, light green for the neutron reflector assemblies, dark gray for the neutron absorber and light gray for the ex-core shield.

The following sections compare the resulting lead activation levels for the two core configurations.

3. MODELLING COOLANT ACTIVATION

3.1. Lead vector

To correctly model the activation of the primary coolant, a detailed composition of the lead and its impurities is required. There are multiple types of lead available on the market graded on their lead purity factor. These types of lead come with tables specifying the maximum allowed concentration of certain elemental impurities given by the manufacturer. For this study an European lead standard PB990R is used as seen in Table I. However, the description of impurities specified by the manufacturer is deemed to be inadequate for this research. More detailed impurity compositions can be determined with mass spectrometry techniques, such as Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) and Glow Discharge Mass Spectrometry (GDMS), as provided in the technical report[6]. In this study

(a) CORE 1

(b) CORE 2

Figure 1. Top-view of the two core configurations at the axial mid-plane. Panel (a) shows the reference configuration (CORE 1) with only reflector assemblies surrounding the fuel lattice. Panel (b) shows the modified configuration (CORE 2) in which additional in-core and ex-core neutron-absorbing shields are introduced to reduce neutron leakage into the reactor pool.

it was deemed that the addition of such impurities has only marginal effects on the coolant activity levels, with the exception of iron (Fe) and Cobalt (Co), for which an initial concentration matching the detection limit of the Mass Spectrometry technique was assumed, i.e., 0.005 ppm.

Table I. PB990R maximum allowed concentration in ppm mass.

Element	Bi	Ag	As	Cu	Sb	Sn	Cd	Ni	Zn
Concentration	100	15	5	5	5	5	2	2	2

3.2. Flux profile and variance reduction

As described in section 2, two core configurations are considered in this study. The CORE 2 layout incorporates additional radial layers designed to limit neutron leakage from the inner core to the surrounding structures. This reduced leakage lowers the neutron activation in the pool and other peripheral components of the reactor.

However, in a Monte Carlo transport calculation, the same feature leads to fewer particles reaching these outer regions, as they are absorbed in the lateral absorber. As a consequence, the stochastic noise on the neutron flux estimates in such regions increases. Such uncertainties have a direct impact on the reaction rates and activation results as explained in subsection 3.3.

In order to reduce the uncertainties in these regions without sacrificing computational power, the global variance-reduction scheme of SERPENT-2 based on weighted windows was applied to the reactor model [8]. This method identifies certain regions in the reactor as being of higher importance. In those regions,

simulated particles are less likely to die off and instead continue with reduced weight. This allows more particles to reach these hard-to-sample areas without increasing the overall computational cost.

To apply this variance-reduction technique, SERPENT-2 is operated in fixed-source mode, following the steps below:

- **Fission source generation:**
A static criticality calculation is first performed to obtain the fission source distribution in the core.
- **Weight-window construction:**
The fission source is then used as a source in an iterative sequence of fixed-source runs. Weight-window maps are generated using three successive iterations to extend the windows into the ex-core regions.
- **Production calculation:**
A final fixed-source simulation run is performed using the fission source together with the last weight-window to quantify the ex-core neutron flux. All results are normalized to the fission source rate obtained from the initial criticality calculation.

The resulting neutron flux distributions are shown in Figure 2, with a top cross-cut view taken at the axial mid-plane of the fuel column. In CORE 2, flux levels in the reactor pool are up to four orders of magnitude lower than in CORE 1. This reduction has a strong impact on the total activity of the lead coolant, as discussed in section 4. For components located outside the core and in the reactor pool, the decrease in neutron flux leads to even greater reductions in induced activity.

Figure 2. Top cross-cut views of the neutron fluxes (in $\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$) in CORE 1 and CORE 2 taken at the axial mid-plane of the fuel column.

3.3. Modeling assumptions in the lead activation equations

The activation of the lead coolant is calculated using Equation 1 with initial conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} N_i(t, \vec{r}) = & - \left(\lambda_i + \int_0^\infty \sigma_{a,i}(E) \varphi(t, \vec{r}, E) dE \right) N_i(t, \vec{r}) + \\ & \sum_j \left(b_{j \rightarrow i} \lambda_j + \int_0^\infty \sigma_{j \rightarrow i}(E) \varphi(t, \vec{r}, E) dE \right) N_j(t, \vec{r}) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where:

- N_i and N_j are the amount of nuclide of i, j present at a give time t and space \vec{r}
- $\sigma_{a,i}$ and $\sigma_{j \rightarrow i}$ are the microscopic neutron-absorption cross-sections of nuclide i and of nuclide i to nuclide j ;
- λ and $b_{j \rightarrow i}$ are the decay decay ratios of nuclide i and from nuclide j to i ;
- ϕ is the neutron flux.

The coolant is treated as stagnant and divided into three spatial zones for CORE 1 and five zones for CORE 2 to capture the gradients in neutron flux, within which volume-averaged reaction rates and nuclide concentrations are computed. Differences in lead activation between a static (stagnant) and a dynamic system are reported in F. Dehlin et al.[4]. The outline of these zones for both cores can be seen in Figure 3 alongside with the side view of the neutron flux.

The following assumptions are made in the model. A time-independent flux representative of the beginning-of-cycle of each core is used, therefore considering it unaffected by lead depletion. Additionally, spatial variations in concentrations and flux are neglected by employing volume-averaged parameters $\langle \rangle_X$ within each zone, as described above. Then, Equation 1 simplifies for each zone X as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \langle N_i(t) \rangle_X = & - \left(\lambda_i + \int_0^\infty \sigma_{a,i}(E) \langle \varphi(E) \rangle_X dE \right) \langle N_i(t) \rangle_X + \\ & \sum_j \left(b_{j \rightarrow i} \lambda_j + \int_0^\infty \sigma_{j \rightarrow i}(E) \langle \varphi(E) \rangle_X dE \right) \langle N_j(t) \rangle_X \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The total specific activity (a) over the four zones is calculated as a volume-weighted sum:

$$a(t) = \frac{\sum_X V_X \sum_i \lambda_i \langle N_i(t) \rangle_X}{\sum_X V_X}, \quad (3)$$

where V_X is the volume of zone X, λ_i is the decay constant of nuclide i , and $\langle N_i(t) \rangle_X$ is the volume-averaged number density of nuclide i in zone X.

4. ANALYSIS OF THE PRIMARY-COOLANT ACTIVATION LEVELS

Figure 4 shows the total activity for both CORE 1 and CORE 2 designs after a simulated reactor operation of 40 years. The activity is plotted in $\frac{kBq}{kg}$ which is the same unit used for the exemption limits provided by national regulatory bodies [7]. Alongside the total activity, the top contributing nuclides are reported. A clear difference in total activity is observed between the two cores, with CORE 2 exhibiting a reduction in primary coolant activation because of the additional shielding. Some isotopes, such as ^{58}Co , show little change between both scenarios. This is because ^{58}Co is primarily produced via the (n, p) reaction on ^{58}Ni , a threshold reaction accessible only to high-energy neutrons and therefore occurring mostly in the inner core. Consequently, the reduction of lower-energy neutron flux in the pool has less effect on its formation.

(a) CORE 1

(b) CORE 2

Figure 3. Lateral cross-cut views of the neutron fluxes in CORE1 and CORE2 taken at the core radial center. The white lines indicate the boundaries of the considered volumes for depletion.

In Figure 5, the activity levels of the two cores are compared by plotting the ratio of the specific activity in CORE 1 to that in CORE 2. The figure also reports the corresponding ratios for the major contributing isotopes. Here the total activity of CORE 1 has been divided over the total activity of CORE 2 to better visualize the reduction in activity in the lead-coolant. The graph of certain elements end when their activity becomes too low. The activity of CORE 2 is six times smaller shortly after operation, decreasing to under four times in the long run. This amount varies based on which nuclide is primarily responsible for the total activity as seen in Figure 4. The amount of change in activity per isotope is dependent on the energy-dependence of the cross-section as discussed previously with ^{58}Co .

To assess the radiological relevance of the predicted activation levels, the results are compared against the regulatory exemption limits defined in the Belgian ARBIS framework [7]. These thresholds determine whether activated materials must remain under regulatory control or can be exempted from further surveillance. The exemption limits are shown in Figure 4 as horizontal reference lines. Two distinct limits apply to the nuclides considered in this study: a higher threshold of 10^4 kBq/kg for ^{204}Tl and ^{205}Pb , and a lower threshold of 10^1 kBq/kg for the remaining nuclides plotted. Among all contributors,

Figure 4. Graph of core activities and the top contributors for decay times following the reactor shutdown after 40 years of operation.

Figure 5. Relative difference in specific activity between the two core configurations, expressed as the ratio of CORE 1 to CORE 2, including contributions from the main activation products.

^{108m}Ag clearly emerges as the limiting isotope with respect to exemption compliance.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study assessed the activation of the primary lead coolant in a lead-cooled nuclear reactor operating below 100 MW, with particular attention to the sensitivity of coolant activation to both in-core and

ex-core shielding configurations. Even with high-purity lead, small amounts of impurities can generate significant activity when exposed to high neutron fluxes in a reactor core over extended periods. Adding additional shielding inside the inner core greatly reduces the neutron flux in both the pool and the outer core, thereby decreasing activation of the coolant and of components located in those regions. However, the majority of coolant activation still originates within the inner core itself, which cannot be avoided.

Although most of the produced radioactive nuclides reach their exemption limits within a few decades, the feasibility of exemption depends strongly on the initial silver content in the lead. Because this study uses the maximum allowed impurity concentrations defined in the European PB990R standard, the actual impurity levels—and therefore the resulting activation—are expected to be lower in practice. A reliable characterization of the silver concentration in a given lead batch is therefore essential for accurately predicting storage and cooling times after reactor operation.

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